

DARIAH ERIC:

Empowering research communities
with digital methods to create, connect
and share knowledge about culture
and society.

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Foreword

It is with great pleasure and a profound sense of pride that we present to you the DARIAH Annual Report for the year 2023. In a year marked by growth and significant new achievements, DARIAH steadfastly continued to pursue its mission of empowering research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society.

2023 was by far the most successful year in DARIAH's history when it comes to securing external funding. The five new Horizon Europe projects including ATRIUM (Advancing Frontier Research in Arts and Humanities), a 10-million€ project which DARIAH coordinates, are bound to substantially improve our operational capabilities and facilitate access to infrastructural offerings throughout Europe.

Last year, we also chaired the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC) in its crucial transition phase between the end of the SSHOC project and the beginning of the cross-cluster project OSCARS. Under our leadership, the Governing Board of SSHOC, consisting of DARIAH, CLARIN, CESSDA, ESS and SHARE, has opened its doors to 6 emerging ESFRI Research Infrastructures, further strengthening the representativeness and accountability of the SSH Open Cluster. We led the technical work on onboarding EOSC services in EOSC Future. And we made our internal procedures more robust by releasing the DARIAH Services Policy and the DARIAH Data Policy.

Member states are the bedrock of DARIAH. In 2023, we welcomed two new countries: Switzerland and Spain. Both joined DARIAH with strong national consortia which enhanced our cultural and linguistic diversity while reinforcing our European infrastructure with new expertise and resources. Collaboration across national and regional borders makes DARIAH uniquely positioned to continue providing a strong thematic contribution to EOSC and Open Science across Europe.

Through the commitment of the working groups and the invaluable contributions of our members and cooperating partners, we have expanded our reach and deepened our impact. The record-breaking DARIAH Annual Event 2023 in Budapest, with its more than 200 in-person participants, fostered an inclusive and thriving environment for scholars and GLAM professionals who joined forces to discuss the role of cultural heritage data as objects of humanistic research.

Together with the Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA), we organised a prominent event on the "Humanities in the Digital Age" at the European Parliament, in which we underscored the vital role of the humanities in securing innovation and empowering democracy.

As we reflect on our achievements in 2023, we are also reminded of the tireless dedication of our core team – the DARIAH Coordination Office. We can't thank them enough for their hard work, their collaborative spirit and their contagious enthusiasm. They are the true heroes of DARIAH.

We invite you to explore this report, not just as an account of our past year's work but as an invitation to engage with us in shaping the future of DARIAH. In 2024, we will be celebrating the 10th anniversary of DARIAH becoming an ERIC. We hope not only to look backwards but also forward. We should be all asking ourselves: where do we want to see DARIAH in the next ten years?

Toma Tasovac

Toma Tasovac

President of the Board of Directors

Chris De Loof

Chris De Loof

Chair of the General Assembly

DARIAH in a nutshell

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) was established in 2006 to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. In 2014 the European Commission awarded DARIAH the status of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Two years later, DARIAH was awarded Landmark Status in the 2016 ESFRI Roadmap as a Research Infrastructure that reached its implementation phase and was considered a pan-European hub of scientific excellence.

Today, DARIAH develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure with 22 Member countries and several Cooperating Partners across six non-member countries in Europe, the US and Egypt. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to, and disseminates research that stems from these

collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

We work across a wide range of arts and humanities research areas and with a diverse range of stakeholders, including academia, GLAM, libraries, technology and education.

Activity Highlights

New Director for DARIAH

On the first of January, we welcomed Agiatis Benardou, Senior Research Associate at the Digital Curation Unit, Information Management Systems Institute, ATHENA R.C. and Postdoctoral Fellow at the Department of Informatics, Athens University of Economics and Business, as a new member of the DARIAH Board of Directors. Actively involved in DARIAH activities since 2009 while the Infrastructure was still in its preparatory phase, Agiatis Benardou worked towards the development of user requirements which provided the foundations for its future design. During the transitional and implementation phases of DARIAH, she initially worked as a member in the Digital Methods and Practices Observatory (DiMPO) and Course Registry WGs, and later chaired the Community Engagement WG. From 2017 until her appointment as Director she co-chaired VCC2, Research and Education Liaison.

January

PALOMERA project kicks-off

A new two-year project, PALOMERA, standing for "Supporting the development of aligned policies for open access books and monographs", kicked off its activities in January, funded under the Horizon Europe call on Reforming and Enhancing the European R&I System. The project will foster the long-overdue inclusion of books in the current European Open Access policy and funding landscapes and is co-led by OAPEN and OPERAS. DARIAH's involvement in the project is concentrated around the data collection and data analysis phases of the project.

Switzerland joins DARIAH as a full Member

Having been a DARIAH Observer country since 2022, in 2023 Switzerland joined DARIAH as a full Member country. The DARIAH-CH Consortium coordinated by the Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) consists of the following academic institutions: Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne and the Universities of Basel, Bern, Geneva, Lausanne, Neuchâtel and Zurich. While Switzerland primarily focuses on the development of a strong and impactful national DARIAH consortium, the collaboration with the Swiss Arts and Digital Humanities community and the support of its research and infrastructural endeavours represents another important national priority.

May

June

Annual Event 2023: Cultural Heritage Data as Humanities Research Data?

With more than 200 participants from over 30 countries around the world, this year's DARIAH Annual Event took place from the 6th to the 9th of June at Eötvös Loránd University in Budapest, Hungary. A key message coming out of the event was the importance of fostering stronger collaboration across cultural institutions in order to best facilitate the integration of cultural heritage data and the management of humanities data.

Launch of the DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue

Featuring a diverse array of resources available to support teaching and research in the sphere of digital humanities, the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue was launched after a long period of preparation. The catalogue was published on the DARIAH website with a search component so that users can browse and access the rich array of over 200 resources available, categorised into Core services and Community services. A communications campaign was launched soon after featuring one tool or service every week on DARIAH's social media, with the hashtag #ToolsServicesThursday, aiming to further highlight these resources among the community.

Successful Spring and Autumn Series of Friday Frontiers webinars

In 2023, we saw the successful completion of one more year of our popular in-house Friday Frontiers series attracting great attendance and engagement. A diverse and exciting array of speakers delivered talks on topics such as digitised formats of popular children's literature; representing, connecting and sharing digital texts; or data journalism and AI. Both series of our webinars allowed researchers, practitioners and stakeholders from across the broad DARIAH community and beyond, to learn about current research, best practice and social impact in digital humanities.

July

DARIAH at DH2023

DARIAH was one of the sponsors of DH2023, the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organisations Annual Conference 2023 which was hosted in July by one of our long standing partner institutions in DARIAH, Graz University, under the coordination of Walter Scholger, National Coordinator for DARIAH-Austria. This year the theme focused on "Collaboration as Opportunity" and many of the DARIAH team members were involved in the programme. DARIAH Director Toma Tasovac served as Programme Committee Chair alongside Anne Baillet (University of Le Mans, France) while DARIAH Director Agiatis Benardou acted as chair and presenter of several sessions. Furthermore, the Bibliographical Data DARIAH Working Group presented their recent findings in a panel entitled "Fostering Collaboration to Enable Bibliodata-driven Research in the Humanities".

September

Spain becomes DARIAH's 22nd Member

After a long preparatory phase from Spain to join DARIAH, in 2023 the DARIAH General Assembly voted unanimously to accept Spain's application for full membership. Following the example of similar successful initiatives in other European countries, the Spanish INTELE strategic network proposed that the CLARIAH-ES national consortium officially integrates Spain into both CLARIN and DARIAH research infrastructures. We are grateful to the Spanish Ministry of Research and Innovation for their support in this process and look forward to collaborating with our Spanish colleagues, aligning national and European priorities and helping arts and humanities researchers thrive in the digital age.

November

December

2023 – Record year in acquiring new Cooperating Partners

Since the redesign of DARIAH's Cooperating Partnership strategy in 2020, 2023 was the most successful year in acquiring new Cooperating Partners. During its two ordinary meetings in May and November, the General Assembly accepted the applications from prestigious institutions from Sweden (Linnaeus University and Uppsala University), the United Kingdom (King's College London, The School of Advanced Study at the University of London, University of Brighton, University of Edinburgh and University of Leeds), Romania (Babeş-Bolyai University) and Egypt (Nile University) to join DARIAH. Each Cooperating Partnership ensures that connection and collaboration with these institutions furthers the advancement of Digital Humanities scholarship.

1. Nurturing and expanding DARIAH's network

a. DARIAH at the national level

In 2023, the National Coordinators Committee (NCC) were happy to welcome two new Member countries, Spain and Switzerland, while they also provided advice to other national consortia who are in the process of joining DARIAH. These efforts were reinforced by the inauguration of a presentation focused on the organisation of each national consortia during NCC Meetings, allowing National Coordinators to share best practices and approach common issues. A step further into more efficient reporting, National Coordinators benefited also from the new Unified National Reports, which combined two reporting processes for InKind Contributions and Key Performance Indicators into one, rationalised process.

Finally, the NCC, with the help and support of DCO staff, worked towards the integration of their national resources into our two catalogues, the SSH Open Marketplace for Tools and Services and DARIAH-Campus for training materials. This work further helped to valorize DARIAH's rich and diverse national landscape at the European level.

Though at different stages in the construction of their national consortia, Luxembourg and Spain made particularly impressive progress in 2023. Their stories are featured below. We are also proud to feature the accomplishments of all of our members, which you can find on the map on pages 8 to 11.

Focus on Luxembourg

Dr. Lorella Viola is a research associate at the Centre for Contemporary and Digital History at the University of Luxembourg, and National Coordinator for DARIAH-LU. She has a background in linguistics and computer science, two parallel strands that blended perfectly in her digital humanities work. During her time as DARIAH-LU National Coordinator, she was able to help relaunch the consortium, with renewed commitments from the Bibliothèque Nationale du Luxembourg and the National Archives. In February 2024, Viola will step down from DARIAH-LU National Coordinator as she will be pursuing a position as Assistant Professor in Digital Humanities and Society at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam in the Netherlands.

Could you introduce us to the role and the work of your consortium?

Luxembourg is a country with an established vision that projects itself into the future, with a large emphasis on digitalization. DARIAH-LU and her partner institutions have benefited from this vision, using generous government support to accomplish impressive digitization projects of cultural heritage and research data. This provided fertile grounds to move forward, as we have two main areas of focus at the moment: Workflows on how to take this cultural heritage data and help researchers exploit it, as well as work with public history. This comprises pedagogical components, but also more broad societal outreach that is shown through digital virtual exhibitions.

What would you consider the 2023 highlights of DARIAH-LU?

We are most proud of the creation of our website, [dariah.lu](#), in 2023. The website is translated into the three national languages of Luxembourg – Luxembourgish, French, German, – and English. We are very proud of this achievement, of convincing our communities to contribute

and share their work with us, and to help take part in this collaborative project. The website was also conceived to be entirely interoperable with DARIAH platforms such as the SSH Open Marketplace, which will be the next phase as we populate content seamlessly on both our website and the SSH Open Marketplace.

Additionally, in November, DARIAH-LU joined forces with C2DH to organise 'The Invi-sible college' workshop. The workshop brought together colleagues from within and beyond the DARIAH community to explore possible collaborations to make better use of DH educational resources as part of the "invisible college". This term commonly refers to a constellation of practices and educational resources for (self)training on digital methods and tools for the humanities that was informally set up to adapt teaching in humanities to fit the digital age. As the first DARIAH-LU official event, the workshop created a roadmap for collaboration between these projects and cognate communities of practice that share DARIAH educational ambitions.

Lorella Viola

Focus on Spain

Dr. German Rigau is Deputy director of HiTZ (Basque Centre for Language Technology), a multidisciplinary research center on Language-centric Artificial Intelligence, based at the University of Basque Country in San Sebastian. Rigau has a background in Computer Science with a doctorate in artificial intelligence from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia. Since September 2023, he is the National Coordinator of the ESFRI European research infrastructures CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-ERIC (CLARIAH-ES).

Could you introduce us to the role and the work of your consortium?

CLARIAH-ES, which officially joined DARIAH on 1 September 2023, is the result of many years of labour in assembling a national consortium, spreading the word around the Spanish research community, negotiating with ministerial bodies, and engaging with DARIAH and CLARIN representatives, both on the European and national level. Organised by the INTELE network, a funded project that brought together the principle actors that would found the consortium, the first challenge was to ensure a geographically and thematically diverse consortium. The University of the Basque Country (EHU) is acting as the National Coordination Institution, leading a consortium made up of the University of Alicante (BVMC), the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC), the National University of Distance Education (UNED), the University of Madrid Complutense (UCM), the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC-CNS), the University of Jaén (UJA), the National Library of Spain (BNE) and the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC).

This broad-ranging consortium, from many of Spain's administrative regions and cultural areas, is both the reason why the Spanish membership in the two infrastructures took some time to negotiate, but also why it will be so strong moving forward, as their support is anchored in multiple levels of the Spanish government. Our organisation allows us to distribute roles and responsibilities, from data providers, such as the BNE and the Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes, to service providers, such as the BSC-CNS, and to data users all across Spain. CLARIAH-ES's goal is to create a comprehensive consortium that harnesses the digital aspects of Spanish research, and is inclusive with as many domains as possible.

What would you consider the 2023 highlights of DARIAH-ES?

The biggest accomplishment is finally joining DARIAH and CLARIN after so much work! Indeed, thanks to all the preparatory work and help from DARIAH-EU and CLARIN ERIC, the transition to membership was smooth, and helped clarify the differences between the two infrastructures.

CLARIAH-ES also hosted a series of events, notably one meeting in June that helped give the final push for the formal adhesion process in Alicante. After the formal acceptance of Spain's candidacy in the two infrastructures over the summer, there was a DARIAH Day event at the BNE on November 7th, which celebrated the official adhesion to DARIAH-EU and included DARIAH Director Agiatis Benardou as a keynote. This coincided with an international conference on Libraries, Data, and AI, which shows once again the breadth of CLARIAH-ES and DARIAH in particular.

German Rigau

CLARIAH-ES Consortium

2023 Highlights from our Member Countries

Italy

At the end of 2023, the first Project Management Board meeting of the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project was held with DARIAH Director Sally Chambers and Nicolas Larrousse agreeing to join the projects' External Advisory Board representing DARIAH ERIC. The project aims to build a federation of researchers, competences, hardware and software resources for the Social and Cultural Innovation research community in Italy and beyond.

Slovenia

In September 2023, a new major industry-adjacent project was launched on "Adaptive natural language processing using large-scale language models", involving a large number of DARIAH-SI partners. The project, funded by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency, aims to develop large-scale language models that affect almost the entire field of artificial intelligence and machine learning, but also have a significant impact on many other areas and the society. This development will provide the fundamental infrastructure for artificial intelligence applications in the Slovenian language.

France

2023 marked the 10th anniversary for Huma-Num, celebrated in a one-day meeting held in Paris in September. The meeting was a success, involving members from DARIAH and other infrastructures (CLARIN and OPERAS) to explore collaborations at the national and the European level. The event was also communicated via CNRS national communication channels.

Luxembourg

2023 marked the formal establishment of the DARIAH-Luxembourg consortium with the National Library of Luxembourg (BnL), the Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C²DH) and the Luxembourg National Archives joining as partner institutions. Another milestone was the launch of the quadrilingual dariah.lu website (<https://dariah.lu/>).

Bosnia and Herzegovina

In May 2023, DARIAH-BiH organised a DARIAH Info Day in the Senate Hall of the University of Sarajevo. The goal of the event was to present the DARIAH-BiH network and the capacities of the consortium members to the public and to promote the infrastructure to national research institutions in the field of social sciences, humanities and arts. The day was captured in a video production, published on the DARIAH-EU Youtube channel (<https://youtu.be/VV4SH6ZNO4Q>).

Denmark

The DeIC Interactive High Performance Computing (HPC) reached a new milestone counting 8000 users in December 2023. The DeIC Interactive HPC has been an incredible success among Danish researchers and students, to the extent that it is now one of the most popular HPC services in Europe, despite being a relatively small infrastructure. This innovative DeIC service has succeeded in democratising HPC among all research disciplines, including humanities and social sciences. It has also been a very popular platform for teachers at universities, who now use it every year as part of their courses.

Germany

- In 2023, the DARIAH-DE repository successfully applied for the CoreTrustSeal (certified since March 2024). CoreTrustSeal is an international, community based, non-governmental, and non-profit organisation promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures. With this certification, the DARIAH-DE Repository demonstrates sustainability, international connectivity and quality assurance.
- In February 2023 the coordination committee of the Association for Research Infrastructures in the Humanities and Cultural Studies (GKFI e.V.), including the National Coordinators of DARIAH, CLARIN and OPERAS, laid out a plan to register and curate all services of the GKFI in the SSH Open Marketplace. This was followed by the publication of guidelines explaining the possibility of adding services and tools to the SSH Open Marketplace under the umbrella of GKFI e.V., an initiative by DARIAH-EU and DARIAH-DE to clearly identify and maintain resources from this ERIC and explained in this poster at the DARIAH annual event 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960885>.

Belgium

- In May 2023, the Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN) hosted the Network Day 2023 on "Imagining the Future of Open Science in Flanders Together: Identifying Priorities in Open Science". FRDN is the Flemish contribution to EOSC and has been very active since its creation. The 2023 Network Day resulted in a booklet publication presenting the outcomes of this day which will be utilised as a starting point for a participatory path within the FRDN to formulate an Open Science vision statement, in anticipation of an upcoming policy period in Flanders (<https://www.frdn.be/network-day-2023/report-network-day-2023/>).

Switzerland

On June 1st, 2023 Switzerland joined DARIAH ERIC as a full Member. This marks a great accomplishment for Swiss researchers as DARIAH provides them a solid and sustainable framework in which they can take active part in European research, exchange and collaborate with European peers in what concerns dealing with the specific challenges of digital methods and Open Research Data in the Arts and DH fields (<https://www.dariah.eu/2023/05/31/switzerland-joins-dariah-as-full-member/>).

Croatia

- In 2023, the eKultura Portal was launched, developed as part of the eKultura project "Digitalization of Cultural Heritage", funded by the European Regional Development Fund. The Ministry of Culture and Media led this project in collaboration with the Croatian State Archives, the Croatian Radiotelevision, the Museum of Arts and Crafts, and the National and University Library in Zagreb. The aim of this portal is to ensure secure storage of digital content and to provide users with easy access to cultural heritage (<https://ekultura.hr/>).
- In October 2023, DARIAH-HR organised the third International Conference on Digital Humanities and Heritage at the University and Computing Center in Zagreb. The conference welcomed more than 50 researchers in a rich programme of workshops, panels, papers and poster sessions. DARIAH Director Agiatis Benardou was invited to deliver the keynote talk to the Conference.

2023 Highlights from our Member Countries

Czech Republic

LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ welcomed new partners in the consortium from the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI), more specifically the Masaryk Institute and Archives of the Czech Academy of Sciences, the National Archive, Terezín Memorial and the Terezín Initiative Institute.

Portugal

The ROSSIO Infrastructure in partnership with the UNESCO Chair “The Cultural Heritage of the Oceans”, presented a Massive open online course (MOOC) on whaling developed by the Portuguese in different geographic spaces, such as Portugal, the Atlantic islands and Brazil, from the Middle Ages to the Contemporary period. The training was live between December 2022 and May 2023, and was organised into four distinct but complementary sections: I) Discovering the natural environment; II) Capture the whales; III) Transform the whales; IV) Preserve, remember and explore the maritime heritage. The MOOC was attended by 476 students (<https://www.nau.edu.pt/en/course/a-caca-da-baleia-e-os-portugueses/>).

Spain

In November 2023, Spain organised a DARIAH-Day event at the National Library of Spain, alongside the Libraries, Data, and AI Conference. The day featured a welcome speech by DARIAH Director Agiatis Benardou on the DARIAH infrastructure, a presentation of the SSH Open Marketplace, papers and posters presenting national projects on Digital Humanities. This event celebrated the official adhesion of Spain to DARIAH-EU.

Serbia

On May 26, the National Library of Serbia organised a workshop on Datafication in Libraries held by Milena Dobrova and DARIAH Director Sally Chambers. The workshop attracted 20 participants and it was the first activity that could indicate the launch of an innovative laboratory for the use and reuse of digital data in the National Library of Serbia.

Austria

- In 2023, CLARIAH-AT launched funding opportunities for junior researchers at MA and PhD level, who have little or no other funding opportunity, who are currently carrying out research in the fields of Digital Humanities. The consortium regards the funding as an investment in the future of Digital Humanities in Austria. Currently, junior researchers can apply for software licences or credits for the service Transkribus required for their current papers and projects as well as travel grants to actively participate in conferences or networking opportunities. So far, four early stage researchers have been awarded funding.

Poland

2023 saw the successful completion of the Dariah.lab project, conducted by 16 DARIAH-PL and partner institutions since 2021, primarily funded through the Smart Growth Operational Programme (with a total budget of approximately 28,000,000 EUR). The tools created within the project found their initial applications, and the final results were presented at the Project Final Conference in October 2023 in Poznań. The DARIAH-PL consortium and the Dariah.lab project received extensive promotion at scientific events, including the DARIAH Annual Event in Budapest, the TRIPLE 2023 Conference, as well as nationwide seminars and conferences (such as the Open Seminar “Season of Digital Humanities”).

Bulgaria

In May 2023, CLADA-BG organised the International Conference on Language Technologies and Digital Humanities: Resources and Applications (LTaDH-RA), with over 30 keynote speakers and presenters from six countries. This was the second edition of the CLADA-BG conference which aims at bringing together NLP developers, linguists, digital humanists, scholars and all parties interested in knowledge modelling and linking data for research.

Greece

The project “The emerging landscape of digital work practices in the Humanities in the context of the European projects DARIAH and CLARIN” ran throughout 2023 with significant results. The project, which was funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.), focused on the analysis of current trends of digital working practices in the humanities in Greece, to support the consolidation of digital working practices by using the services of the national infrastructure APOLLONIS and to continue the cooperation with the European infrastructures DARIAH and CLARIN, for the benefit of the research communities in Greece and Europe.

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Sustaining a Digital Humanities Infrastructure and Network for Austria

What did we do?

Since its inception in 2019, the CLARIAH-AT consortium, representing the Austrian universities and research institutions which coordinate and drive Austrian activities related to the ESFRI research infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH, has rapidly built a reputation for excellence and cooperation.

The latest evidence of the Austrian Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)'s confidence in CLARIAH-AT's proven track record of success, is the approval of a project which aims to provide the Austrian DH community with the collaborative infrastructure required for the future development of the use of digitised data, research software and data science in humanities and cultural studies research ([DHInfra.at](https://www.dhinfra.at)).

Overview

A collaboration between the Austrian universities of Graz, Innsbruck, Klagenfurt, Krems, Salzburg and Vienna, the Austrian Academy of Sciences and the Austrian National Library, CLARIAH-AT brings together Austrian institutions with relevant expertise in research, development and teaching in the field of Digital Humanities as well as in the establishment and sustainable operation of research (data) infrastructures, which also play an active role in the development of Austrian Digital Humanities in general. Based on these stakeholders' experience and a consultation of the Austrian professional DH community, the consortium authored a vision for the further development of Austrian Digital Humanities, along the four respective pillars of *Research infrastructures and networks*, *Research data and repositories*, *Methods, services and tools* and *Education, training and knowledge transfer*.

Closely tied to these focal points, the consortium has engaged in several activities to bring their vision to life. A dedicated funding call on "[Interoperability and Reusability of DH Data and Tools](#)", financed through the Austrian Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)'s support dedicated to CLARIAH-AT and the consortium's membership fees, led to the realisation of 16 projects which were all implemented in late 2023 or early 2024, with a total budget of 382.777 Euros.

Why did we do it?

Through collaboration and sharing of expertise and resources, CLARIAH-AT aims to foster DH research and engagement with digital academic resources, not only among scholars and professionals but also the general public.

Who did we do it for?

CLARIAH-AT activities, services and expertise are aimed at and open to the entire Austrian Digital Humanities community, regardless of their affiliation to one of the CLARIAH-AT consortium partner institutions.

Furthermore, the CLARIAH-AT consortium forms the backbone of the DHInfra.at project: in 2022, the Austrian Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) issued the call "(Digital) research infrastructures", a call for proposals for the sustainable development of universities in the context of digitalisation, funded with support from the EU's Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), aimed at the expansion, modernisation and/or acquisition of high-quality (digital) research infrastructure at Austrian universities.

[Digital Humanities Infrastructure Austria \(DHInfra.at\)](#) is building an infrastructure for digitally supported research in the Austrian humanities. It fills the gap between standard offers in cultural heritage institutions (digitisation), in research data management (curated and integrated repositories vs. institutional repositories), in software solutions (subject-specific open source products), and in HPC infrastructures common in the natural, technical and life sciences regarding the processing of large amounts of data with machine learning methods.

Equipment for digitisation (scanning robots, multispectral cameras) and storage (Ceph) for repositories for data from memory institutions, as well as GPU clusters for the research-driven development and productive use of machine learning methods are procured and implemented. Open source software is also developed and customised to meet the specific needs of the DH community.

The CLARIAH-AT consortium facilitates the governance and long-term maintenance of the infrastructure and makes it available to the Austrian DH community at large, taking its inspiration from examples like the Danish DeIC Interactive HPC infrastructure (<https://www.deic.dk/en>).

The DHInfra.at project was **one of 19 out of 69 submissions approved**, and the only project which was accepted without any budget cuts, receiving funding of 2,2 million Euro (in addition to the consortium partners' in-kind contributions of approx. 1 million Euro). As the ministry evaluation put it, this was largely due to the CLARIAH-AT consortium's involvement:

“[DHInfra.at] draws on the proven CLARIAH-AT consortium with well-established decision-making processes and is therefore also connected to the European infrastructures CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-EU.”

Description of the Impact

In the years since the CLARIAH-AT consortium was established, considerable progress has been made in establishing, fostering and sustaining Digital Humanities activities in Austria. In addition to (and as part of) the project call above, CLARIAH-AT has hosted several Schools, Workshops and other training events. University Master Programs and Professors for Digital Humanities have been established at the Universities of Graz and Vienna (with their holders taking an active role in the consortium itself) over the last 7 years. Highly competitive ERC grants have been awarded to Austrian Digital Humanities researchers (among them the aforementioned professors).

Another tangible result of CLARIAH-AT's reputation and efforts in community building are close cooperations with Austrian Cultural Heritage institutions and organisations ([Museumsbund.at](#), [Time Machine Organisation](#), ...). CLARIAH-AT has also been invited to join the Austrian National advisory board of the [UNESCO Memory of the World](#) programme. Furthermore, the speaker of the CLARIAH-AT consortium is an elected member of the Board of the [Association of Digital Humanities in the German-speaking Areas \(DHd\)](#) - evidence of both the standing of CLARIAH-AT in the Austrian DH community and the standing of the Austrian DH community in the German-speaking areas.

A particular highlight in July 2023, was that the University of Graz hosted the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organisations (ADHO) [Digital Humanities 2023 conference: Collaboration as Opportunity](#) (DH2023) which attracted 872 participants. DARIAH-EU was one of the two main sponsors of this conference, and CLARIAH-AT contributed additional sponsorship. An even more visible contribution of DARIAH-EU to the success of this conference was the role of DARIAH-EU's President of the Board of Directors Toma Tasovac as one of the DH2023 program chairs, sharing his expertise, passion and visionary [reflections on revolutions](#) with the global community.

In addition to these examples of the appreciation of the national and international DH community, the consortium's reputation with national ministries and funding agencies is documented by these bodies' presence in CLARIAH-AT's [Advisory Board](#) and the success of project submissions closely affiliated with the consortium: as mentioned above, the DHInfra.at project, which is establishing a joint infrastructure for digital research in the humanities in four fields and develops and implements the governance required for its use, and is being made available to the Austrian national DH community, sustained and managed through the CLARIAH-AT consortium.

Evidence of the Impact

As demonstrated above, CLARIAH-AT and Digital Humanities in Austria are a remarkable success story. The CLARIAH-AT consortium itself has become a stakeholder recognised by Austrian Federal Ministries, national UNESCO bodies and Cultural Heritage associations.

The professionalisation of the consortium is evident in the [Digital Humanities Austria Strategy 2021+](#) and the financial commitment of the Austrian consortium institutions which is in turn backed up by funding from the Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research (BMBWF).

It is evident that CLARIAH-AT's involvement has directly affected the evaluation and success of submissions in highly competitive national funding calls demonstrating its national impact. Furthermore, highly visible Austrian contributions to the international Digital Humanities community - from hosting the ADHO Digital Humanities 2023 conference in Graz to occupying leadership positions in international associations and the European Infrastructure consortia DARIAH-EU (e.g. Matej Durco as Chief Technical officer) and CLARIN-ERIC - demonstrate Austria's international reputation.

b. DARIAH Cooperating Partnerships: An important milestone towards full adhesion

2023 was a productive year for DARIAH Cooperating Partnerships, with nine new institutions joining across four countries. Two longtime Swedish partners, Linnaeus University and Uppsala University, renewed their Cooperating Partnerships as part of an effort to have their national infrastructure, Huminfra, apply for national Membership.

“The DARIAH Cooperating Partnerships over the last eight years played a seminal role in demonstrating the value of DARIAH to our communities and convincing the Swedish Research Council to apply for the national membership through the national Huminfra infrastructure in 2024”,

added Koraljka Golub of Linnaeus University. We also welcomed five new partners from the UK, who are also working to reestablish contacts in the European Research Area through DARIAH. Finally, we welcomed the Babeş-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca, Romania as well as Nile University in Egypt, the first institution in an Arab country. The Cooperating Partnership with UNED of Spain ended on September 1st, when the country joined DARIAH as a full Member.

Beyond welcoming new partnerships, DARIAH continued to follow up with existing partners and integrate them further into the DARIAH community. Most importantly, DARIAH participated in several events organised by our Cooperating Partners in 2023, including two DARIAH Days and two meetings with ministry officials to help advance the process of obtaining National Membership for these potential Member countries. More specifically, these events included a DARIAH Day at the University of Helsinki as part of the Finnish DARIAH-FI annual meeting, including a workshop focused on onboarding Finnish resources into the SSH Open Marketplace in April, a presentation on DARIAH and its benefits to the Latvian community at the CLARIN-LV Day in September, and a keynote at the IESA DARIAH Day and strategic planning meetings with the Slovakian DH community to jumpstart plans on a DARIAH-SK consortium in October. DARIAH Officer for National Coordination Edward Gray was also present in Reykjavik for a ministry meeting in Iceland, which coincided with a trip to help inaugurate the Centre for Digital Humanities and Arts in the brand new EDDA building on the University of Iceland campus.

These meetings helped to introduce DARIAH more widely to the respective national research communities while communicating the benefits of joining and participating in the infrastructure as a member country, an institution or as individual researchers. They also served to show the commitment that DARIAH-EU has to facilitating National Membership and setting up national infrastructures, which we hope to see prosper in each of these countries in the coming years.

DARIAH-EU also proudly renewed its partnership with Princeton University, which had reached the end of its initial three-year term. This productive partnership led to a series of “New NLP” workshops which demonstrated a shared commitment to enhancing resources and capacity for multilingual work in the digital humanities community, as well as the “Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies Summer School” in July 2023 in Athens.

c. Projects

DARIAH actively participates in several European projects funded by the European Commission to reinforce its strategy and empower research communities in the Arts and Humanities. In 2023, DARIAH was involved in seven active projects as a partner. Furthermore, the portfolio grew with four newly funded projects to kick off in 2024, one of which is coordinated by DARIAH.

OPERAS-PLUS

Kicked off in September 2022, this project aims to support the further development of the research infrastructure OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities) in its preparatory phase and on its way towards becoming an ERIC. Within OPERAS-PLUS, DARIAH is addressing the problem of the perceived prestige of innovative outputs in academia. A wide range of outputs in Digital Humanities is still not considered in formal peer review and research evaluation mechanisms. DARIAH is preparing case studies, particularly on the overlay journal model, which is an innovative type of scholarly publication that operates on top of pre-existing data repositories and preprint servers. Case studies are then integrated to the OPERAS Innovation Lab, which provides a knowledge hub on novel scholarly communication.

PALOMERA

This two-year initiative started in January 2023 to investigate challenges that prevent open access to academic books. Contrary to article publishing in journals, academic books have not been a focal point for open access. The PALOMERA project aims to provide resources to support funder and institutional policies for open access books. To do so, the project relies on the collection of qualitative and quantitative data on the open access book policy landscape in Europe. Structuring the work around a comprehensive and well structured data management plan is paramount in such a project, and DARIAH contributed with OAPEN to deliver this document in the first months of the project. DARIAH also helped in performing qualitative interviews and collecting material on open access policies regarding books that, in a successive step, were made available for further in-depth analysis. According to the findings, evidence-based recommendations for aligning policies regarding open access books in Europe will be produced and disseminated towards the end of the project.

CLS INFRA

In 2023, DARIAH continued its work in the CLS INFRA project, mainly in the management of the transnational access (TNA) programme which offers the opportunity to scholars to obtain access in one of the project partner institutions around Europe to conduct a funded research fellowship with a focus on Computational Literary Studies methods. This year, two calls were launched, which saw a total of 24 scholars being awarded. Since the beginning of the project in March 2021, the interest in this programme grew quite significantly and 45 visits have been arranged so far, exceeding the initial expectations.

A second Training School *Digging for Gold: Knowledge Extraction from Text* was organised on 9-11 May in Madrid at UNED premises. Participants were able to learn more about information extraction techniques in order to improve their textual analysis skills.

Finally, DARIAH is currently working to provide comprehensive and easily implementable recommendations and templates covering the Research Data Life Cycle, highlighting research good practices in the context of CLS corpora. The results of this ongoing work will be made available via a Wiki distributed under an open licence before the end of the project.

ERIC Forum 2

2023 saw the start of the second ERIC Forum project with the aim of further structuring the cooperation between the ERICs and supporting the implementation of the ERICs' Policy in the European Research Area (ERA). The project is divided into four main pillars: reinforcing the European research infrastructure policy; implementing the ERIC Regulation, strengthening capacities and identifying possible shared resources; coordinating communication towards various stakeholders; developing an online platform reflecting the data, information and knowledge on the ERICs. DARIAH took the lead on the latter point and is working on identifying data and features that should be available in the platform through qualitative interviews and stakeholders analysis. The findings will serve as a basis for developing user-requirements and designing the platform. Once ready, the platform will contain a wide range of data about ERICs that will help stakeholders in visualising the impact of ERICs in the European research landscape.

TRIPLE

The TRIPLE project concluded in March 2023 with the final release of GoTriple, a discovery platform for the Social Sciences and Humanities. The platform provides a single access point to explore, find, access and reuse materials such as literature, data, projects and researcher profiles at European scale.

On 27-28 March 2023, DARIAH organised the event *Use of vocabularies for metadata curation and quality assessment in social sciences and humanities*. The aim of the event was to analyse the challenges faced by the partners to create the multilingual GoTriple vocabulary and compare it with other initiatives carried out in the Social Sciences and Humanities branch of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) context. The event targeted experts already knowledgeable in the field coming from different initiatives such as OpenAIRE, EUROPEANA and SSHOC. The slides of the event were made openly available on DARIAH-Campus.

EOSC Future

This project, running from April 2021 until March 2024, aims to integrate, consolidate, and connect e-infrastructures, to further develop the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

DARIAH leads a task on *Integration of Community Services and Products into EOSC*. The goal of the task is to ensure the integration of EOSC-Core services and external providers services who need to connect to the EOSC platform. The work led to the publication of a report that outlines how external providers from ESFRI Research

Infrastructures or Science Clusters can integrate EOSC-Core Services with their own service offer. Furthermore, the EOSC Service Provider's Maturity Model has been developed, in order to assess the level of integration with the EOSC for any provider interested to join and also provides best practices for increasing that maturity. This workflow has been published and is available on the SSH Open Marketplace.

DS4CH – European Data Space for Cultural Heritage

The common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage is an initiative of the European Union, funded under the European Union's Digital Europe programme. The project, running since September 2022, deploys the data space for cultural heritage, building on and expanding the existing functionalities and services of the Europeana Digital Service Infrastructure. EUROPEANA coordinates the work of 18 partners from nine EU countries. DARIAH has the aim of increasing the visibility of cultural heritage offer to academic and research communities, by creating a SSH Open Marketplace workflow on Collections as Data and providing a DARIAH-Campus course on using Europeana API's in Research and Higher Education.

In 2023, DARIAH was successful in receiving funding for four new project proposals. The role of DARIAH in these projects, as coordinator or project partner, is essential to strengthening its long-term strategy, developing new collaborations and reinforcing existing ones with a wide range of actors in the European Research Area.

JANUARY

ATRIUM

ATRIUM stands for Advancing Frontier Research In the Arts and Humanities. The project counts on four leading European Infrastructures, DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN and OPERAS to provide improved access to a rich portfolio of state-of-the-art services available to researchers across countries, languages, domains and media. It will also offer the opportunity to scholars to apply for training visits to receive mentoring in one of the ATRIUM partners facilities.

JUNE

ECHOES

ECHOES aims to create the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), a shared platform for heritage professionals and researchers to access data, innovative scientific and training resources and advanced digital tools co-developed by the heritage community according to their specific needs.

OSCARS

The project regroups world-class research infrastructures, organised in five "Science Clusters", ENVRI-FAIR (environmental science), EOSC-Life (life science), ESCAPE (astronomy and particle physics), PaNOSC (neutron and light source science) and SSHOC (social science and humanities) to rise the efficiency and productivity of researchers by providing open data services and infrastructures for discovering, accessing, and reusing data.

AARC TREE

The project is focused on Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructures (AAI) which are fundamental to enable federated access to resources. The main objectives are to capture and analyse new Authentication and Authorisation interoperability requirements, provide a landscape analysis of AAIs services, define new technical and policy guidelines and expand the number of research communities that can implement the Authentication and Authorisation for Research Collaboration (AARC) model.

JANUARY

MARCH

d. DARIAH and the EOSC

Making sure that Arts and Humanities research remains at the heart of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) developments has been one of the main motivations for DARIAH in 2023. Science Clusters – see <https://science-clusters.eu/> – like the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC), of which DARIAH is a driving member, demonstrated how instrumental their role is in fostering collaborations between the Research Infrastructures within their domains to build a meaningful EOSC for researchers. In 2023, DARIAH efforts in the EOSC-Future project have also enabled the needs of the Arts and Humanities community to be better taken into account in the deployment of the EOSC federation.

Chairing the SSH Open Cluster

At the end of 2022, DARIAH President of the Board of Directors, Toma Tasovac, was elected Chair of the SSH Open Cluster and worked alongside the Vice-Chair Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, Director of CESSDA ERIC. Following the establishment of a Memorandum of Understanding supporting the Cluster collaboration, in 2023, the Cluster focused on installing rules of procedure as well as on launching regular General Assemblies gathering all members.

The SSH Open Cluster allows Research Infrastructures to speak with a common voice on the EU scene, towards the European Commission, the EOSC Association or in the ESFRI EOSC task force. For example, in 2023, SSHOC answered to the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Landscape analysis for the SSH, and has also proven to be a fertile environment to develop new projects, with some successes to start in 2024.

In addition to that, the Cluster enables shared support and maintenance for key services that benefit the research community, like the SSH Open Marketplace. For 2023, the joint support of DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA for the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace translated into the organisation or participation in more than 15 community events. The co-located workshop to the DH2023 Conference in Graz “How to create DH workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace?” was a great example of how this shared SSHOC service can trigger both conceptual discussions on the best way to represent and document digital methods and be a place where actual implementation and sharing of research workflows happens.

With almost 200 new active contributors gained in 2023, for more than 1,000 entries created or enriched in the catalogue, the SSH Open Marketplace has kept its promise to serve the research community by reflecting existing practices and enabling the discovery of new resources for its users. This work would not have been possible without the efforts of the community and the Editorial Team that gathers curators, moderators and domain experts in SSH.

EOSC-Future: Bridging Science Cluster and the nascent EOSC EU Node

In 2023, thanks to the leadership of DARIAH Director, Sally Chambers, in the EOSC-Future project, an important step was taken in the long term Open Science evolution in Europe. Indeed, within this project, a crucial partnership developed between the EOSC Core, the Science Clusters and their related ESFRI Research Infrastructures through the onboarding and integration of service and data source providers into the EOSC Exchange. The team involved – DARIAH alongside e-Infrastructures, other RIs and supported by ACDH-CH and the GWDG as affiliated entities – developed EOSC service integration workflows and tested their operationalisation. In addition to that, and to prepare the transition between the EOSC-Future project and the upcoming EOSC EU Node, scenarios for Migration of EOSC Providers and their Resources were jointly developed by the EOSC Future Handover Team, in close liaison with the European Commission.

Finally, an initial analysis for a Service and Data Sources Portfolio per Science Cluster was conducted which will provide a baseline of the Science Clusters Services and Data Sources Portfolio. This work will be further iterated and developed in the follow-up project **OSCARS, Open Science Clusters’ Action for Research and Society project** which will kick off in 2024.

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Cross-Cluster Collaboration: DARIAH engaging the research community in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

What did we do?

Research infrastructures, such as DARIAH, play a crucial role in engaging the research community with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Within the EOSC Future project, DARIAH, in close collaboration with the Science Clusters, developed and implemented workflows to integrate their services and data sources into EOSC, resulting in an EOSC Service Provider's Maturity Model.

Why did we do it?

During EOSC Future, a critical mass of services and data sources from across the Science Clusters were successfully onboarded. This ensures that EOSC supports both a wide array of scientific disciplines and domains, but also facilitates innovative, interdisciplinary research by providing easy access to high-quality data and state-of-the-art tools.

Who did we do it for?

The Science Clusters, representing the research communities from a broad range of disciplines (Astronomy and Particle Physics, Environmental Sciences, Life Science, Photon and Neutron Sciences and the Social Sciences and Humanities) across Europe.

Overview

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), like any other infrastructure, only becomes valuable once it is used by the research community. With 63 ESFRI research infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap, including 41 Landmark (operational) Infrastructures, such as DARIAH and 22 emerging infrastructures, it is essential that the services and data sources that these research infrastructures provide are fully leveraged in the context of EOSC. The design and implementation of the service and data source integration workflows within the EOSC Future project has been crucial to interconnect the EOSC Core Services with the research services provided by the Science Clusters. Through an analysis of good practices and lessons learned during the development of these workflows, it was possible to derive recommendations for ongoing work beyond the EOSC Future project. This analysis led to the development and publication of a EOSC Service Provider's Maturity Model, which can be used by individual ESFRI Research Infrastructures, by the Science Clusters and other EOSC Service providers, to self-assess the maturity of their integration into the EOSC ecosystem. This work ensures that domain-specific knowledge remains firmly embedded in EOSC.

Description of the Impact

By the end of EOSC Future, the Science Clusters have successfully used these *services and data source workflows* to onboard and integrate over 150 resources from across the disciplines to the *EOSC Catalogue and*

Marketplace Environmental Sciences (ENVRI-FAIR): 81 services and five data sources; *Life Sciences* (EOSC Life), 15 services and three data sources; *Astronomy and Particle Physics* (ESCAPE): six services and five data sources; *Photon and Neutron Sciences* (PANOSC): seven services and *Social Sciences and Humanities* (SSHOC): 33 services and three data sources. These onboarded services will be used as the basis for the *Resources Hub* for the EOSC EU Node which is scheduled to be launched in 2024. The metadata about the onboarded services and data sources will also be published as an open science dataset to make it available for reuse.

The DARIAH-led approach to onboarding and integrated services will be used as the basis for creating a **Services and FAIR Data Portfolio per Science Cluster** in the OSCARS, Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society project which started in early 2024 (<https://oscars-project.eu>). Additionally, the DARIAH Services Policy, which is closely aligned with EOSC, has already been shared with other research infrastructures beyond the Social Sciences and Humanities, both as inspiration for their own service management and in preparation for their contribution to the EOSC Federation (Durco, M., Barbot, L., Tasovac, T., Tóth-Czifra, E., Roi, A., Chambers, S., Benardou, A., Constantopoulos, P., Dobрева, M., Scharnhorst, A., Kálmán, T., Rißler-Pipka, N., & McConville, A. (2023). DARIAH Services Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184825>).

Finally, the EOSC Service Provider's Maturity Model has also been successfully utilised by the Science Clusters in relation to the "composability" of services and data sources through the creation of reproducible research workflows. Such workflows, as exemplified by the workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace, will also be used as a further approach to engage researchers with EOSC in the context of OSCARS (Workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow>).

Evidence of the Impact

DARIAH has been taking a strategic and sustainable approach to service management for a number of years now. Through active participation in EOSC Future, DARIAH has been able to take the lead on the integration of services and data sources from all five science clusters (EOSC-Life, ENVRI-FAIR, ESCAPE, SSHOC and PANOSC).

Such achievements have been recognised both within the SSHOC cluster:

"The coordination efforts undertaken by DARIAH in the EOSC Future project to inventorise the services and data sources from the Science Clusters have paved the way for the Services and FAIR Data Portfolios that the Science Clusters will elaborate on in the OSCARS project to contribute to the EOSC ecosystem through thematic service federation."

Franciska de Jong, Senior Advisor, CLARIN ERIC (SSHOC Science Cluster).

Photo by Patrick Perkins on Unsplash

And beyond:

"There has been considerable focus on the 'Cloud' of EOSC. Now is the time to turn our attention to putting the 'Science' into EOSC. The work to onboard and integrate services and data sources from the Science Clusters, so that they can potentially be used in any combination, led by DARIAH in EOSC Future is a crucial step towards developing reproducible research workflows based on open science practices within the context of EOSC."

Christos Arvanitidis, Chief Executive Officer, LifeWatch ERIC (ENVRI Science Cluster).

This successful cross-cluster collaboration is further underscored by the awarding of the OSCARS project, where DARIAH, together with PANOSC, will co-lead the ongoing activities to engage the European research community, through our collaborative infrastructural efforts in EOSC.

* Chambers, S. (2023): Putting the Science into EOSC: the Service Provider's story. <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1nymKGm4313CzGI0WGqbiYL-WxzD9jGXX/edit?usp=sharing&oid=115020870043056556446&rtpof=true&sd=true>

* Chambers, S., Barbot, L and Kirnbauer, M (2023). EOSC Service Providers Maturity Model: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/pig9Nt>

* Durco, M., Barbot, L., Tasovac, T., Tóth-Czifra, E., Roi, A., Chambers, S., Benardou, A., Constantopoulos, P., Dobrova, M., Scharnhorst, A., Kálmán, T., Rißler-Pipka, N., & McConville, A. (2023). DARIAH Services Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184825>

2. Activities and results

a. Working Groups

The DARIAH Working Groups are a good reflection of the diverse and rich landscape of the interdisciplinary research carried on in the arts and humanities, and in particular within the DARIAH infrastructure. In 2023, DARIAH counted 14 active Working Groups, including a new Working Group that joined the community over the year, the ARCHitectural HERitage Thesaurus through Integrated digital Procedures and Open data (ARCHETIPO) Working Group. In the focus box on the next page, we spotlight this new Working Group along with insight from the chairs, Elena Gigliarelli and Georgios Artopoulos.

Over 2023, 12 workshops were hosted by various DARIAH Working Groups, such as the joint DARIAH-CLARIN workshop “Infrastructures, DH and Industries” that took place at the CLARIN Annual Conference in Belgium in October. The workshop included a presentation from the Digital Humanities Course Registry Working Group, delivered by two of the co-chairs, Iulianna van der Lek and Anna Woldrich. The Theatralia Working Group has also organised several workshops throughout the year, including a hybrid scientific conference, “Performing Arts: Transitioning to the Digital Age,” that took place in Croatia in March 2023.

Several of the initiatives DARIAH Working Groups spearhead include the ongoing support and maintenance of tools, thesauri, databases, and repositories. For instance, various scholarly portals are managed and updated by members of the Digital Numismatics Working Group. Over 2023, the Thesaurus Maintenance Working Group maintained updates to the BBT (Backbone Thesaurus); via collaborations with Tezaurus.hr and DARIAH-HR, they also co-delivered a

workshop related to building and managing thesauri. Over the course of 2023, the Women Writers in History Working Group (in collaboration with the international NEWW Network) successfully migrated the NEWW-VRE at the Huygens Instituut to the SHEWROTE database at Radboud University and will continue to help coordinate this resource. Finally, the Multilingual DH Working Group launched their Living Bibliography of Multilingual DH as a Zotero group library, a growing, open resource that is a truly transnational initiative supported by DARIAH.

The visibility of DARIAH Working Groups within the domain of digital humanities is broadly captured across various publications, including articles, reports, websites, and external funding calls. The Research Data Management Working Group finalised their publication “Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community” as both a static PDF and an interactive website. Following the analysis of questionnaires and various workshops focussed on identifying the training requirements for PhD candidates in digital humanities, the Community Engagement Working Group released a report titled, “Training needs, skills and awareness of existing resources among PhD students”. Finally, the Digital Practices for the Study of Urban Heritage (UDigiSH) Working Group not only participated in multiple funding calls outside of DARIAH, but also contributed a chapter to the upcoming Placemaking in Practice trilogy on the topic of heritage-based storytelling and communication.

Following a successful application from the 2021 Working Groups funding call, both the #dariahTeach and Ethics and Legality in Digital Arts and Humanities (ELDAH) Working Groups successfully collaborated on the “Social Justice in Digital Humanities” project. Part of this initiative

included open calls for projects to be included in the project output, resulting in case studies from 18 different projects as well as a toolkit. The outputs from this project were highlighted at the DARIAH Annual Event in 2023 and will soon be available widely. Finally, the members of the Biographic Data Working Group began work on the project “Open Bibliodata Workflows” after successfully receiving

DARIAH Theme funding in early 2023. Their work resulted in completing six workflows while a related publication on these efforts is forthcoming.

The figure on the previous page illustrates the DARIAH Working Group Outcomes in 2023.

Focus on the new Working Group ARCHETIPO, “ARCHitectural HEritage Thesaurus through Integrated digital Procedures and Open data”

2023 saw the start of a new Working Group: ARCHitectural HEritage Thesaurus through Integrated digital Procedures and Open data (ARCHETIPO), chaired by Elena Gigliarelli (Senior Scientist at the ISPC Institute of Heritage Sciences of the CNR National Research Council of Italy) and Georgios Artopoulos (Associate Professor, Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center, Cyprus Institute).

This Working Group has methodological ties with other relevant Working Groups (such as BiblioData, ELDAH, DiMPO, and #dariahTeach) while content and tool-wise shares common ground with the UDigiSH Working Group. ARCHETIPO is chaired by the two heads of VCC3 on Scholarly Content Management, members of the Joint Research Committee (JRC), and already has support from institutions/experts in Italy, France, Portugal, and Cyprus.

The ARCHETIPO Working Group aims to explore (new) methods of documenting architectural heritage. Its practical aspect is to facilitate discourse leading to the creation of ‘a digital platform for the representation and management of heritage data on historic buildings in Europe’ – HERIGITAL.

The Co-Chairs of ARCHETIPO, Elena Gigliarelli and Georgios Artopoulos, weigh in on the momentum behind creating the ARCHETIPO Working Group and where the Working Group contributes to DARIAH.

What was the motivation for establishing the ARCHETIPO Working Group?

ARCHETIPO was established to address a gap in the use of digital representations in the architectural heritage documentation sector. Digital technologies are revolutionising the way we preserve, conserve and study cultural assets, but specific methods still need to be developed for documenting and managing digital representations and datasets related to historic buildings.

In response to this need, we established the Working Group ARCHETIPO with the aim of promoting innovative workflows that integrate digital procedures and open data for the creation of a thesaurus dedicated to architectural heritage. Our intention is to bridge the gap between digital documentation technology and cultural heritage preservation, enabling better preservation, understanding, and valorisation of our architectural past.

How does the ARCHETIPO Working Group contribute to DARIAH’s goals as an ERIC?

The ARCHETIPO Working Group fits perfectly into DARIAH’s mission to promote advanced research in the humanities through access to resources and the development of digital skills through training material. Our Working Group aims to develop and share innovative methodologies for the knowledge representation of architectural heritage, thereby contributing to the growth of knowledge in the field of digital humanities.

Additionally, we actively collaborate with other Working Groups and national and European institutions to promote the adoption of better data standards and practices in the field of cultural heritage conservation. Through our commitment to creating the ARCHETIPO Thesaurus and promoting the use of open data and integrated digital procedures, we contribute to advancing research and promoting the valorisation of European cultural heritage, aligning with DARIAH’s goals as a European research infrastructure.

Elena Gigliarelli

Georgios Artopoulos

b. Education and Training

DARIAH-Campus

DARIAH-Campus (<https://campus.dariah.eu>) is the central resource within DARIAH for free and open training resources in a broad range of topics related to digital arts and humanities, launched initially in 2019, with a major update to the publishing process and content management system completed in 2021. It serves two functions: it is a **discovery framework** for training resources that exist within the DARIAH eco-system, and; it is a **hosting platform** for training resources created by DARIAH-affiliated individuals, institutions and projects.

In 2023, the DARIAH-Campus site welcomed 3,921 people visiting the site in 4491 sessions. The majority of traffic is through people accessing the site by a direct link (that is typing, or copying and pasting the link directly into the URL bar). In 2023, there were more referrals via social media than there had been in 2022, indicating that campaigns via X, YouTube and LinkedIn are successful in driving traffic.

Of the visitors to the DARIAH-Campus site, the overwhelming majority came from Croatia, followed by Austria and Germany. The United States, Japan and Brazil also featured in the top 20 countries that visited the site in 2023, indicating a more international appeal to the resources available.

In 2023, a total of 34 new resources were published to DARIAH-Campus in a variety of topics. For example, the GeoHumanities Working Group produced a very practical step-by-step course as a hosted resource on DARIAH-Campus, outlining the workflow for conducting geospatially motivated analysis of texts using QGIS, while the Ranke2.lu project from the University of Luxembourg published their “From the Shelf to the Web, Exploring Historical Newspapers in the Digital Age” module as an external (catalogued) resource.

There was also an increase of large collections being proposed or contributed to DARIAH-Campus from projects and research infrastructures such as EHRI (the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure), and dariahTeach. In these cases, they were existing DARIAH-Campus contributors who were returning to add additional materials. However, in December 2023, DARIAH-Campus also welcomed Programming Historian to its list of contributors, further solidifying its position as a trusted and prestigious platform for online training resources in the digital arts and humanities.

In March 2023, DARIAH was invited to present on DARIAH-Campus at the European Commission “A Cloud for all” event that aimed to kick-start the formation of a community of practice between cultural heritage professionals¹. During the session on “Capacity building for training opportunities on IT skill”, DARIAH Director Toma Tasovac discussed five lessons learned from DARIAH’s engagement in the pedagogical landscape:

Users to DARIAH-Campus Globally and at European Level in 2023

¹ EU Commission “Cloud for all” event – <https://research-innovation-community.ec.europa.eu/events/13Rq0jrNgOrkH49gjMVavN/overview> retrieved 10th April 2024

1) Investing into training and education is the best way to ensure the social sustainability of research and data infrastructures, which is why **capacity building should be built into the very idea of the provision of services**; 2) **Technology is not the ultimate challenge**: reluctance to adopt new, open methods is primarily a social and cultural challenge; 3) **Documentation is not the same thing as training**: teaching tools is important, but teaching methods even more so; 4) Teaching tools in isolation from each other is not enough: **in research, workflows rule supreme**; and 5) In order to close the gap between better and lesser-resourced institutions and communities, research infrastructures should **develop coherent, integrated curricula around their services**.

DARIAH-Campus was also represented as part of the wider suite of DARIAH tools and services available to researchers at the ADHO Digital Humanities Conference in Graz in July, with members of the DARIAH team available to provide hands-on demonstrations and walk-throughs of the DARIAH-Campus content management system, resulting in new publications to the platform.

Training Tuesday Campaign

In 2023, the Training Tuesday campaign continued on X (Twitter), to highlight the training materials on DARIAH-Campus. The campaign ran from February to December, once again with a 6-week break over the Summer period, highlighting 31 different resources over the course of the year. In total, the tweets received over 32831 views, with over 1100 'likes' and 136 'retweets', and resulted in 379 'click-throughs' to the resources. This is an increase on the engagement and traffic generated via X (Twitter) in 2022. The resources from Training Tuesday are also highlighted in the monthly DARIAH Newsletter, showcasing the resources that were featured in that month's Training Tuesday campaign, thus adding a further means of promotion for both DARIAH-Campus and the individual training resources. As part of the concerted strategy to increase engagement across social media platforms, the #TrainingTuesday features were also posted to LinkedIn from July 2023 onwards. As followers and engagement increased in that platform, this helped to widen the reach of Training Tuesday, boosting engagement with DARIAH-Campus through LinkedIn.

Training Tuesday Campaign Analytics

Year	Total tweets	Impressions	Total engagements	Likes	Click throughs	Retweets	Engagements : likes	Engagements : click throughs	Engagements : retweets
2022	30	20610	527	148	120	75	0.281	0.228	0.142
2023	33	32831	1144	353	379	136	0.309	0.331	0.119

Friday Frontiers

The 2023 Friday Frontiers series ran successfully in Spring and in Autumn/Winter, and were public for the full year for the first time. This continues from the 2022 Autumn/Winter series where they were made public for the first time, following DARIAH's strategy of engaging and ensuring more open resources for training events and materials beyond the DARIAH community.

The topics covered in the 2023 Friday Frontiers webinars were once again varied, demonstrating the broad scope within DARIAH. In March 2023, the Spring 2023 series kicked off with Magda Wnuk and Marta Świetlik showcasing their 'Queen of Humanities' project that opened up a new way of publishing projects. In April 2023, Anne Baillot reassured us that we could learn and love digital text in four easy steps, reviewing the ways in which AI can support research in textual analysis. Then in May, to finish off the Spring 2023 series, Bahareh Heravi from the University of Surrey discussed issues around Data Journalism and AI.

In the Autumn/Winter 2023 series, there was a strong storytelling and cultural heritage theme, beginning in October with Stella Wisdom from the British Library who talked through the curatorial issues related to their recent 'Digital Storytelling' exhibition. In November the storytelling continued as Maria Goiceochea de Jorge from the University of Madrid demonstrated the 'Digital Editions of Children's Stories', specifically translations and reworkings of Edith Nesbitt's 'Plague of Dragons' books. The year of Friday Frontiers finished with Nasrine Olson from the University of Borås, Sweden, who highlighted the challenges that people with mobility, visual and/or hearing impairments may experience when engaging with the world, and how recent projects from the Centre for Inclusive Studies have sought to address these.

Overall in 2023, the Friday Frontiers webinars attracted an audience of over 180 people during the live events, with additional people viewing the recordings when they were later published on DARIAH-Campus.

c. Investing on Open Science

DARIAH's position on the Role of Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform

In 2023 DARIAH published a position paper showing its strong support for the **reform of research assessment** (The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper. 2023, <https://hal.science/hal-04136772>). This paper is the result of close collaboration with CoARA and shows the need to strengthen thematic RIs evaluative cultures to address important scholarship that is invisible in formal assessment. RIs could be key in helping research-performing organisations, funders and other stakeholders go beyond the publication-based proxies such as impact factors and citation counts.

Implementation of DARIAH Data Policy

Alongside DARIAH Service policies, the **DARIAH Data Policy** produced in December 2023 (version1) outlines the basic principles for managing and sharing research data within the DARIAH infrastructure and beyond. The policy targets both data producers and data providers, encourages the use of open formats and community standards, acknowledges the diversity of options for data publishing, and puts forward practical recommendations for publishing DARIAH-affiliated data in trustworthy repositories with the goal of making them discoverable through the OpenAIRE-Graph.

An interview with Françoise Gouzi, DARIAH's Open Science Officer

In September 2023, we welcomed Françoise Gouzi as the new DARIAH Open Science Officer. Based in Toulouse, Françoise is responsible for defining the strategy and initiatives behind the Open Science pillar of DARIAH.

Could you tell us about your previous engagement with Open Science and arts and humanities infrastructures?

As Information specialist, with a degree in History and Information Sciences and specialised in Open Science, I was in charge of Open Science for over 10 years at the University of Toulouse Jean Jaurès in SSH and Arts. I contributed to the Open Science Policy and supported researchers and doctoral students, spread over 23 units and Arts and Humanities disciplines, with training and education in collaboration with the Library and the University Presses. Since 2008 I have been very active in national and international infrastructures and networks on Open Science (French Ministry of Research, CNRS, OpenEdition, Latindex, DOAJ, ...), and based both on my ground experience and my professional network, I have become an expert in open publishing, Diamond Open Access and evaluation. Joining DARIAH represents a real opportunity for me to advocate Open Science as a common good at European and infrastructure level and support Arts and Humanities communities in their transition towards Open Science practices.

Building on all the significant work done in the past years for supporting the DARIAH community towards transitioning to Open Science practices, could you please describe what is your strategic vision for Open Science in DARIAH?

When joining DARIAH, I first hand experienced that DARIAH's commitment to Open Access and Open Science is remarkable. Promoting widespread dissemination of knowledge by enabling researchers, students, and the general public to access a wealth of information free of charge and, more often than not, without login requirements is crucial.

My strategic vision is to continue supporting open scholarly communication for SSH communities and to enhance Open Access for monographs and Diamond Open Access model. This will be achieved by fostering strong collaboration with our European counterparts, in European projects that DARIAH is leading (e.g. ATRIUM) or is a collaborative partner (CLSIinfra, PALOMERA, OPERAS Plus). Through these projects, where I'm currently contributing on building tools on data sharing for researchers (CLS Infra), creating recommendations and policies on Open Access Books (Palomera) and an evaluation framework for innovative outputs, I hope to strengthen our Open Science Policy (on data and culture heritage) and evaluation framework.

To conclude, what are your plans for 2024 and which missions do you want to achieve in this role?

In 2024, I will be focusing on creating a robust framework for open peer review assessment of different research outputs as a contribution toward maximising the quality and impact of Arts and Humanities research in Europe. I will be also working towards setting up a DARIAH Action Plan for CoARA, contributing thus to reforming the Research assessment framework.

One overarching initiative to achieve these objectives will be the launch of "Transformations", DARIAH's overlay journal. This journal, which will be hosted on Episciences – <https://www.episciences.org/> – (provided by one of DARIAH's French partner institutions), will enable researchers to publish a diversity of Digital Humanities forms and outputs – datasets, digital editions, workflows, software, training materials – that they usually don't get enough academic credit for. In 2023 we were doing all the preparatory work on this, which is aligned with the 3rd Strategic Action Plan and the "Manifesto on Science as Global Public Good" (signed in December 2023).

With this innovative publishing form, we aim to reinforce sustainability and reproducibility of research by proposing a transparent and ethical publishing model based on Diamond Open Access and Open Peer Review, promoting best practices and editorial quality standards and finally improving metadata quality of open repositories from DARIAH member states.

Françoise Gouzi

d. Creating Tools and Services for the Community

2023 represented a major milestone for the DARIAH Infrastructure. Indeed, while the EU scene of Research Infrastructures constantly evolves – see the DARIAH in SSHOC and EOSC section – DARIAH developed a framework that aims at ensuring the best integration possible of the resources produced or offered across its network into a coherent ecosystem for the benefit of researchers. The DARIAH service management is taking shape along those lines, and two major achievements marked the 2023 year: the **publication of the DARIAH service policy** and the **release of the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue**.

DARIAH Service Policy

The publication of the DARIAH Service Policy – see Durco, M., Barbot, L., Tasovac, T., Tóth-Czifra, E., Roi, A., Chambers, S., Benardou, A., Constantopoulos, P., Dobrev, M., Scharnhorst, A., Kálmán, T., Rišler-Pipka, N., & McConville, A. (2023). DARIAH Services Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184825> – is the result of a large consultation with all DARIAH bodies and proves the professionalisation and maturity of DARIAH as a social and technical distributed research infrastructure.

The DARIAH service policy has been designed to respect the diversity and richness of the services offered throughout the 200 partner institutions, cooperating partners and individual researchers involved in DARIAH Working Group activities, while introducing principles and processes coming from the wider IT service management environment. Especially, the lightweight IT service management (ITSM) “standard” FitSM has been used as an inspiration to identify and clearly define roles and responsibilities of the various actors involved in the DARIAH service management processes, though it has not been strictly adopted as it does not fit with the very distributed environment and limited human resources available to implement this policy.

Even though individual DARIAH partners act largely autonomously regarding the provision of their services, the exchange within and central coordination of the network allows DARIAH: a) to work towards a consolidation of the service offer, including identifying and eventually closing any gaps, and b) to share the load between individual partners, potentially shifting the service provision between nodes of the network in response to changed capacities or other local conditions. This mechanism supports service sustainability by offering a perspective for continuation to services developed in funded projects that are otherwise in danger of getting abandoned once projects end.

The strategy for sustainability of the service offer is also one of the drivers behind the DARIAH service policy, which defines procedures for managing services in the DARIAH distributed environment. It distinguishes two main categories of services:

Core services (12) are mature services owned by DARIAH ERIC and operated primarily by DARIAH partner institutions. These services enable the infrastructure to carry out its mission and support its strategic priorities. Examples: SSH Open Marketplace (marketplace.sshopencloud.eu), DARIAH-Campus (campus.dariah.eu).

Community services (240) are owned by one or more DARIAH partner institutions and are contributions from the national nodes to the ERIC, or outcomes of projects or other DARIAH-affiliated activities, especially the DARIAH Working Groups. Examples: Image annotation tool (ima.coders.tools), DARIAH-DE Geo-Browser (geobrowser.de.dariah.eu) or Backbone Thesaurus (BBT) (backbonethesaurus.eu).

The main goal of the service policy is to clarify what can be considered a DARIAH service and to describe the coordination and management of the DARIAH distributed infrastructure in terms of service offer and provision across the network.

DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue

Building on the DARIAH service policy, it was possible to compile the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue (dariah.eu/tools-services/tools-and-services), which was released in 2023 and that provides access to more than 200 tools and services. These resources, produced by the DARIAH community, support researchers in all stages of the research process – creation, discovery, enrichment, processing, analysis, visualisation and publication. They correspondingly cover a wide range of service types: data repositories, catalogues, services for processing, analysing and visualising data, as well as platforms for knowledge sharing and scholarly communication.

Reusing the (meta)data coming from the SSH Open Marketplace, the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue is considered a subset of this wider discovery portal and only features tools and services produced by and of interest to the DARIAH community. This compilation of resources relies on an agreement about the way catalogue entries are collectively used and described as summarised in the *Guidelines for adding DARIAH National Resources to the SSH Open Marketplace* (see Annual Report 2022).

To allow for easier browsing and navigation through the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue, we have implemented filters to support search by: DARIAH National node; concepts of the Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities (TaDiRAH, tadirah.info); EOSC resource categories.

The release of the DARIAH Tools and Services catalogue in 2023 was only possible thanks to the involvement of the DARIAH National Coordinators and their teams, who contributed to create and enrich the catalogue entries; the members of the Editorial Board of the SSH Open Marketplace, who guided the contributors and moderated the content; and the development team of the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), especially Norbert Czirjak, who developed the catalogue on the DARIAH website. Publishing this catalogue on the DARIAH website resulted in more exposure of the DARIAH Tools and Services, as well as in more traffic to the DARIAH website and the tools and services pages as they ranked among the most visited pages in 2023.

Diving into the DARIAH Services

The DARIAH service policy and catalogue allowed us to dive in and explore in more detail what the DARIAH tools and services collection consists of.

What does the DARIAH service offer actually consist of?

Among the 200+ community services, 27 languages are mentioned as being supported (interface language and/or languages processed by the tools). In terms of obtaining an overview of the type of tools and services and the activity type of research they support, we filtered the community services by the most used TaDiRAH activities and EOSC categories, as shown in the tables below.

TaDiRAH activities	Number of catalogue entries using this concept
Disseminating	53
Discovering	33
Searching	32
Browsing	26
Storing	23
Data Visualization	22
Digital Publishing	21
Publishing	18
Enriching	17
Analyzing	15
Archiving	13
Annotating	11
Writing	11
Preserving	10

Apart from the immediate exposure of the tools and services through the DARIAH services catalogue on the DARIAH website, in 2023 we also launched a communication campaign, #ToolsServicesThursday, featuring one community service every week on DARIAH's social media, thus allowing the DARIAH audience to dive into the diversity that the catalogue offers.

In addition to that, specific initiatives are also designed and organised to reinforce synergies between services of the same nature. For example, the DARIAH tools and services catalogue references a number of Skosmos (skosmos.org) instances publishing controlled vocabularies used by the DARIAH community, and synergies have been explored to bridge these services to the SSH Vocabulary Commons initiative in 2023 (see the *Use of vocabularies for metadata curation and quality assessment in Social Sciences and Humanities* workshop materials available on DARIAH-Campus, <https://campus.dariah.eu/resource/events/use-of-vocabularies-for-metadata-curation-and-quality-assessment-in-social-sciences-and-humanities>).

Efforts conducted in 2023 to clarify the DARIAH service management paved the way to a better integration, i.e. in terms of exchange of information, between DARIAH national and EU catalogues, and this topic will be at the heart of the DARIAH-EU activities in 2024.

EOSC categories	Number of catalogue entries using this concept
[access to] Scientific/Research Data	31
Software	30
Sharing and Discovery	24
Repository	19
Processing and Analysis	17
Education and Training	12
Digital Preservation	10
Data Archives	10
Publication	9
Discovery	5
Data Analysis	5

e. Connecting Communities: The DARIAH Annual Event 2023

The DARIAH Annual Event took place in Budapest, Hungary, from June 6th to 9th, 2023. For this event, DARIAH Director, Sally Chambers, Chair of the Programme Committee, presented the community with the theme “Cultural Heritage Data as Humanities Research Data?”². Inspired by the proclamation “cultural heritage data is humanities research data”, this DARIAH Annual Event sought to explore what this means in practice and broaden the scope of digital humanities research.

Our local hosts for 2023 were the Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE) Faculty of Humanities and the National Laboratory for Digital Heritage team. This Annual Event returned to a largely in-person format, supported with some pre-recorded video and live-streaming of all plenary sessions. The live-streaming was supported with a Discord server, also hosted by the local organisers, which enabled participants who were viewing remotely to participate such as by asking questions during sessions or contacting other remote participants.

For many years the DARIAH Annual event has been a combination of a community meeting and a scientific conference. The conference part is increasingly growing and for 2023, we received 126 submissions of which over 100 were accepted as papers, panels and posters. As was the case in the Annual Event of 2022, we set another record of in-person participation with over 200 participants, pointing to the growing digital humanities community. Furthermore, our geographically diverse participant list indicates the important role of DARIAH worldwide, as several (presenting) participants who attended are based outside of Europe.

The structure of the event followed a similar format to previous years, allowing for internal DARIAH meetings, open to the wider community Working Group meetings, paper sessions, panel sessions, poster and demo sessions, plenary sessions and keynotes. The opening keynote on Wednesday, June 7th, was delivered by Thomas Padilla (Deputy Director at Archiving and Data Services of the Internet Archive) entitled ‘A Mutualistic View of AI in the Library or a Continuation of Craft’. Meanwhile, on Friday, June 9th, a closing keynote panel entitled ‘DARIAH Data Spaces Dialogue: Imagining Experimental Data Spaces for Analysis of Cultural Heritage Using Digital Methods’, was chaired by DARIAH Director Sally Chambers.

DARIAH Annual Event 2023, CC BY

2 Chambers, Sally, Gábor Palkó, Francesca Morselli, Kim Ferguson, and Andrea Scharnhorst (2023). Book of Abstracts, DARIAH Annual Event 2023: Cultural Heritage Data as Humanities Research Data?. Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8340670>.

f. DH2023: “Cooperation as Opportunity”

The ADHO Digital Humanities 2023 conference “Cooperation as Opportunity” took place from 10th to 14th July 2023 in Graz, Austria. Hosted by the University of Graz, with programme chairs Anne Baillot (University of Le Mans, France) and DARIAH President of the Board of Directors Toma Tasovac, the conference attracted close to 800 on-site (and another 100 online) participants. The conference buzzed with colleagues arriving from 45 countries in 6 continents, who joined eager for exchanging knowledge, gaining new insights and networking, presenting a total of 540 submissions in different formats. One of the highlights was the keynote speech by DARIAH Scientific Board member Professor Sarah Kenderdine, entitled “Two-Fold Revolutions: Computational Museology in the Age of Experience”.

Sarah Kenderdine

Walter Scholger of Graz University, coordinator of DH2023 and National Coordinator for CLARIAH-AT, commented:

“Bringing the international ADHO DH conference to Graz was an amazing experience. Our community could not wait to reconnect with each other, and to share and discuss the topics we love with our colleagues from across the globe. It also showcased the ground-breaking work not only by the Austrian DH community, but also our colleagues from South-Eastern Europe – alongside the beautiful scenery and sights that Graz has to offer.”

DARIAH Participation and Representation

DARIAH was well represented across the week: Director Agiatis Benardou chaired and presented several sessions, while former Directors Jennifer Edmond and Frank Fischer also spoke, chaired, and presented posters during the Thursday evening poster session. Training and Education Officer Vicky Garnett chaired the Thursday morning panel on “Collaboration” while Officer for Service Development and Integration Laure Barbot led the Tuesday pre-conference workshop entitled “Creating a DH workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace”. Finally, the Bibliographical Data DARIAH-EU Working Group presented their recent findings in a panel entitled “Fostering Collaboration to Enable Bibliodata-driven Research in the Humanities”.

Throughout the week, DARIAH shared a booth with CLARIN, where the team provided information about ways in which to collaborate with the wider DARIAH community, explore and engage with DARIAH Tools and Services, foster new connections with attendees of DH2023, and promote DARIAH-Campus.

Image by Leonhard Niederwimmer from Pixabay

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

DARIAH-EU Cooperating Partnership creates opportunities for Digital Hellenic Studies

What did we do?

In July 2023, the Summer Institute in Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies, facilitated by DARIAH and co-organised by the Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton University, the Seeger Center for Hellenic Studies, the UNESCO Chair for Digital Methods in the Humanities and Social Sciences at Athens University of Economics and Business (AUEB), and the MSc in Digital Methods for the Humanities programme at AUEB, trained scholars from Princeton and Greek Universities in digital tools and methodologies to advance research in Hellenic cultural heritage.

Why did we do it?

The Summer Institute in Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies, held in Athens from July 3-7, 2023, aimed to empower scholars with vital digital skills and methodologies. By fostering collaboration between international institutions, it advanced research capabilities and bolstered efforts to safeguard and promote Hellenic cultural heritage in the digital age.

Who did we do it for?

The workshop was open to Princeton affiliates as well as students and scholars from universities or cultural heritage institutions in Greece.

Overview

The Summer Institute on Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies marked the beginning of a collaboration between Princeton University, a DARIAH co-operating partner, and Athens University of Economics and Business (AUEB), to explore innovative digital methodologies in the study of Hellenic culture. Hosted by the Seeger Princeton Center, in partnership with the UNESCO Chair for Digital Methods in the Humanities and Social Sciences (AUEB) and the MSc Program in Digital Methods for the Humanities (AUEB) this five-day workshop aimed to catalyse interdisciplinary research and foster international networks and collaborations.

The workshop gave scholars the opportunity to explore DH theories, methods, and techniques to advance their own research projects. Instructors from Princeton's Center for Digital Humanities and the MSc Program in Digital Methods for the Humanities at AUEB served as instructors, providing both theoretical background as well as technical guidance for DH project design. The workshop provided a conducive environment for scholarly exchange and hands-on learning. Participants, including scholars, students, and cultural heritage professionals from both Princeton University and Greek institutions, engaged in lab-style sessions and were invited to bring and present their own digital research initiatives and collaborate on them with the group.

In essence, the Summer Institute in Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies served as a pivotal platform for advancing digital scholarship, fostering cross-cultural exchange, and empowering scholars of various academic levels to address contemporary challenges in the study and preservation of Hellenic cultural heritage.

HOME
SCHEDULE • RESOURCES
PEOPLE

Summer Institute: Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies

July 3 - 7, 2023

This workshop will give scholars the opportunity to explore digital humanities (DH) theories, methods, and techniques to advance their own research projects. Instructors from Princeton's Center for Digital Humanities and the MSc Program in Digital Methods for the Humanities at the Athens University of Economics and Business (AUEB) will serve as instructors, providing both theoretical background as well as technical guidance for DH project design.

THE CENTER FOR DIGITAL HUMANITIES PRINCETON
SEEGER CENTER FOR HELLENIC STUDIES
DARIAH-EU
UNESCO

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Description of the Impact

The Summer Institute on Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies has fostered collaboration, innovation, and interdisciplinary exchange, which all align with DARIAH's Strategic Pillars.

Here are some key aspects of its impact:

Fostering Collaboration and Networking: The event provided a platform for scholars of various career levels to collaborate on projects, share resources, and build networks across institutions and disciplines. This collaboration led to the development of innovative digital projects and research initiatives, such as exceptionally good Master's Theses submitted by Greek participants, which would not have been as feasible without the interdisciplinary exchange facilitated by the Summer Institute on Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies.

Training and Education: The Summer Institute on Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies offered training activities on digital tools, methods, and best practices, equipping participants with the skills and knowledge needed to further incorporate digital humanities approaches into their own research and teaching. This training helped to bridge the gap between traditional humanities scholarship and digital methodologies, empowering scholars to harness the potential of digital technologies in their work.

Interdisciplinarity and Innovation: Bringing together scholars from diverse backgrounds, ranging from classics to computer science, the event stimulated a vibrant community of interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation by fostering dynamic exchanges of ideas and methodologies. Through hands-on exercises and games, and focusing on collaborative projects, participants explored new frontiers in digital humanities, forging connections between traditional Hellenic studies and cutting-edge technological tools.

Evidence of the Impact

"Being exposed to such an interdisciplinary and transnational environment challenged and inspired me. So far, as a DH student, I had only interacted with Greek colleagues and academics. My master's thesis would not have been the same had it not been for this event – and it was also so much fun!"

said Sofia Kastanidi, a postgraduate student in Digital Humanities in AUEB, while Vicky Dritsou, one of the local instructors, added,

"In our session in this Princeton/AUEB event, which would not have taken place had it not been for DARIAH, we decided to teach a difficult conceptual model using a card game: it's always more pleasant to learn by playing and it's even more pleasant to teach by playing! Nothing like watching your students enjoy a course!"

Teaching and games aside, the event featured a round table discussion, in which DARIAH Directors Toma Tasovac and Agiatis Benardou had the opportunity to discuss the Digital Humanities landscape in Greece vis a vis Europe with Panos Constantopoulos (UNESCO Chair for Digital Methods in the Humanities and Social Sciences at AUEB and Chair of the DARIAH Scientific Board) and Natalia Ermolaev (Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton University). The discussion was attended by a number of invitees, including Professors in various Greek institutions, as well by the Rectors of two major universities in Athens, AUEB and Panteion.

The success and impact of the Summer Institute in Digital Humanities for Hellenic Studies is further demonstrated by the fact that AUEB will be officially joining DARIAH-GR in the coming funding cycle, as well as by the fact that, in 2024, a second Summer Institute will be organised, this time focusing on methods for analysing the textual culture of the Greek world from antiquity to the present.

3. Doing things right and doing the right things

a. Measuring our impact

For the past five years, DARIAH has been collecting a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators which capture our achievements, measure the organisation's development, and demonstrate the depth and richness of DARIAH's value and impact.

DARIAH's current set of KPIs is composed of 10 quantitative indicators across three high-level categories - Usage, Effectiveness, Impact - and is based on data collected from our national consortia and at European and international level. These quantitative indicators are complemented with the annual DARIAH Impact Case Studies as their qualitative counterpart.

Three Impact Case Studies were also produced for the year 2023:

- Sustaining a Digital Humanities Infrastructure and Network for Austria (cf. p. 12-13)
- Cross-Cluster Collaboration: DARIAH engaging the research community in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (cf. p. 18-19)
- DARIAH-EU Cooperating Partnership creates opportunities for Digital Hellenic Studies (cf. p. 30-31)

In this section, we aim to provide our stakeholders with an accurate picture of the performance and impact of DARIAH at a European scale for the year 2023. It is important to mention that while we have been constantly refining our methodology and data collection process, the year 2023 was a turning point in the latter. We have indeed developed a web application to simplify the reporting exercise for the 22 national coordinators on the one hand and the processing of the collected data on the other hand.

USAGE

In 2023 we welcomed 2 new members, Spain and Switzerland. Switzerland has been an observer for the past three years. A slight increase in the number of collaborating institutions can be observed, which demonstrates the constant expansion of the national consortia. Although the number of contributors is slightly lower than last year, we have seen a sharp increase in the number of events organised within the national consortia (1,826 in 2023 vs 1,237 in 2022) as well as in our event audience, showing a constant growth of the

DH community aware of and participating in DARIAH activities. At the end of 2023, 188 training materials were available on the platform DARIAH-Campus, reflecting the growing richness and diversity of the training offer. The number of platform interactions reached a new record in 2023, with more than 301 million page views across the range of service offered at national (294) and European level.

EFFECTIVENESS

The third DARIAH Strategic Action Plan, which officially started on 01.06.2022 for a total duration of 3 years, is composed of 13 high-level goals. On 31 December 2023, we had completed 69% of it.

IMPACT

In terms of impact, the number of publications increased significantly (+32%), returning to the 2021 level, illustrating the growing production of knowledge thanks to the services and tools offered by the infrastructure. Funding leverage has doubled between 2022 and 2023, demonstrating the ability of some national consortia to win increasingly large projects, reflecting the significant continuous investment of our member countries in Digital Humanities.

b. Changes in the organisation

Following Jennifer Edmond's departure on 31 December 2022 after two consecutive terms, the Board of Directors entered 2023 with a new line-up: Toma Tasovac, Sally Chambers and Agiatis Benardou, who was appointed by the General Assembly in November 2022. The new trio provided leadership to the organisation and secured funding through successful project proposals throughout 2023.

Some changes were also noted within the DARIAH Coordination Office. A significant change was the departure of the Open Science Officer, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, in May 2023 after 5 years of dedicated work. Her successor, Françoise Gouzi officially started on 1 September 2023. Following that, in June 2023 the CIO team saw the departure of Francesca Morselli. Francesca was instrumental in raising the profile of Working Groups within DARIAH, work that will be continued by the other members of the CIO team. On a lighter note, the Outreach and Communications Officer, Eliza Papaki, was on parental leave from June and was replaced by Amelia McConville.

While there were no changes in the Scientific Board in 2023, the Joint Research Committee has grown by welcoming three new members Maria Ilvanidou, Carmen Di Meo and Tomasz Umerle.

4. Looking Ahead

As DARIAH-EU casts its gaze forward, we envision a landscape ripe with collaboration, openness, and innovation. The new decade finds DARIAH expanding in capacity, enjoying great successes, appreciating risks and challenges, accommodating growth and strategic shifts, and reflecting on its ever-evolving values and goals.

Building upon our mission to enhance and support digitally-enabled research in the arts and humanities, we aim to continue fostering interdisciplinary dialogue and advancing cutting-edge methodologies in existing and new research domains. In the coming times, DARIAH-EU aims at further building its user base, while deepening the engagement with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and augmented reality, leveraging these new workflows to expand current boundaries of scholarly inquiry. Moreover, as the digital landscape evolves, DARIAH-EU remains committed to promoting open access to cultural heritage data and fostering sustainable practices in digital scholarship.

Collaborative initiatives with CLARIN, ARIADNE and OPERAS, as well as with partner institutions and organisations across Europe, the USA and Egypt, are and will remain paramount. Furthermore, we are looking forward to welcoming more countries as full members and as co-operating partners. We are anticipating the formal formation of Regional Hubs, which will contribute to the expansion of DARIAH through meaningful engagement with non-affiliated institutions in non-member countries. The near future holds promise for DARIAH-EU in terms of increasing outreach and accessibility, with a fresh focus on engaging the arts communities and on promoting digital literacy among underrepresented research communities.

Through strategic partnerships, innovative projects, and a steadfast commitment to our Strategy and core values of inclusivity and openness, DARIAH-EU is poised to navigate the challenges and opportunities of the next year, shaping the future of research in the digital arts and humanities across Europe and beyond. We are looking forward to it all!

Appendix

Appendix I: Administrative and Legal Details

Who's who in DARIAH

Body: Board of Directors

Toma Tasovac
Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities

Agiatis Benardou
Digital Curation Unit, IMSI, ATHENA R.C./Athens University of Economics and Business

Sally Chambers
Ghent University

Body: Scientific Board (as of 31st December 2023)

Panos Constantopoulos	Chair of the DARIAH Scientific Board, Athens University of Economics and Business
Payal Arora	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Marko Demantowsky	University of Vienna
Martine Denoyelle	Institut National de l'Histoire de l'Art
Milena Dobрева	GATE Institute
Alain Heures	Virtuology Academy
Sarah Kenderdine	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Andrew Perkis	NTNU ARTEC

Body: Joint Research Committee

Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH / DANS
Tibor Kálmán	Heads of VCC1	GWDG
Tomasz Parkola		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Maria Ilvanidou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, IMSI, ATHENA R.C.
Tanja Wissik		ACDH-CH
Georgios Artopoulos	Heads of VCC3	STARC, Cyprus Institute
Elena Gigliarelli		CNR National Research Council Italy
Adeline Joffres	Heads of VCC4	TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS)
Carmen Di Meo		OVI-CNR institute
Tomasz Umerle	Member of the JRC	Institute of Literary Research, Polish Academy of Sciences

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office	
Francesca Morselli Integration Officer	
Amelia McConville Community Engagement Officer	
Eliza Papaki Outreach and Communications Officer	
Marco Raciti European Project Manager	
Simon Saldner Integration Officer	
Andrea Scharnhorst Chief Integration Officer	
Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra Open Science Officer	
Anne Grésillon Chief Organisation Officer	

* Shaded area marks colleagues that changed positions or left DARIAH before the end of 2023

Body: National Coordinators Committee		
Nanette Rißler-Pipka	Chair of NCC / Germany	Göttingen State and University Library
Martin Lhoták	Vice Chair of NCC / Czech Republic	Czech Academy of Sciences
Mörth Karlheinz	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Walter Scholger	Austria	Center for Information Modeling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, University of Graz
Christophe Verbruggen	Belgium	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Lana Paćuka	Bosnia and Herzegovina	University of Sarajevo
Dimitar Iliev	Bulgaria	Sofia University
Kiril Simov	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Kristoffer Laigaard Nielbo	Denmark	Aarhus University
Nicolas Larousse	France	Huma-Num
Paris Potiropoulos	Greece	Academy of Athens
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	Italian Council of Research
Lorella Viola	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Claudia Borg	Malta	University of Malta
Richard Zijdeman	Netherlands	International Institute of Social History (IISH)
Karolina Brylska	Poland	University of Warsaw
Amelia Aguiar Andrade	Portugal	NOVA FCSH
Snežana Petrović	Serbia	Serbian Academy for Sciences and Arts
German Rigau Claramunt	Spain	HiTZ, Basque Center for Language Technology
Jakob Lenardič	Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History
Rita Gautschy	Switzerland	Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH)

Appendix II: Finances

1) DARIAH ERIC

a) Preliminary remarks

It should be noted that, at the time of writing this annual report, the accounts of DARIAH ERIC for the year 2023 have not yet been audited. DARIAH's General Assembly traditionally reviews the auditor's report and decides on the financial statements at its November 2024 meeting. It should be nonetheless mentioned that the last report of the auditor in 2022 concluded that DARIAH's financial statements "give a true and fair view of the assets and liabilities, and of the financial position of the organisation on 31 December 2022 and of the results of its operation in accordance with the accounting rules and principles applicable in France."

However, this does not preclude us from already giving an accurate situation of DARIAH's finances for the year 2023 that reflect its operations in an understandable and transparent manner for its stakeholders.

It is important to clarify that in this first section "DARIAH ERIC", only the resources and expenses related to DARIAH's core activities – i.e., without its participation in European projects – are accounted for. Besides, due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations.

b) Resources and financial overview

22 member countries contributed to DARIAH ERIC's budget 2023 in two different ways: through cash and in-kind contributions. In accordance with the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amounted to:

2023 total cash contribution	839,165 €
2023 total in-kind contribution	5,038,141 €

The total income 2023 is mostly composed of cash contributions from member countries and overheads of European projects that have been completed and paid in full. In 2023 this applied to the project TRIPLE (GA-Nr: 863420), completed in March 2023 and the project ERIC Forum (GA-Nr: 823798), completed in December 2022.. Moreover, the financial support of CLARIN and CESSDA for the development of the SSH Open Marketplace, as well as various reimbursements (VAT, unused funding, etc.), contributed to DARIAH's total revenue in the year 2023.

With a total income of 961,197 € and a total expense of 946,908 €, DARIAH's balance for the year 2023 is as follows:

DARIAH balance 2022	813,380 €
DARIAH income 2023	961,197 €
DARIAH expenses 2023	946,908 €
Balance 2023	14,289 €
Total balance	827,669 €

c) Focus on the expenses

In 2023, the operational costs are distributed as follows:

Type of costs – DARIAH only	2023
Personnel costs	697,705€
Travel and accommodation	55,445€
Core service	47,739€
Community support through project funding	36,254€
Catering	21,089€
Membership in eu organisations	20,750€
Financial support to partner events	15,131€
Communication	14,469€
Accounting and audit	13,088€
Oa monograph bursary	9,426€
Equipment and consumables	4,010€
Training	3,144€
It development	2,500€
Legal advice	2,175€
Conference organisation	1,500€
Bank charges	1,308€
Conference fees	1,175€
Total	946,908€

The largest component of DARIAH's operational costs is by far the personnel which represents 73.7% of the total costs. The second largest item of expenditure (5.9%) are the travel and accommodation costs. 2023 was again very active in terms of representation and event, among which the yearly Annual Event which took place in Budapest. Just behind in third place come costs linked to core services (5%), i.e. primarily costs associated with the maintenance and development of the SSH Open Marketplace and, to a lesser extent, internal communication tools such as emails, Zoom, Google Workspace, Basecamp, etc. The fourth largest item of expenditure, with 3.8%, is the financial support to research communities which refers to tailored project

funding for scholars in the arts and humanities. In 2023, the topic of the DARIAH thematic funding was 'workflows'.

It is interesting to mention that the item "Membership in EU organisations" refers to fees paid to be part of the EOSC association, the OPERAS infrastructure or the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH). It may be also useful to clarify that under the heading "financial support to partner events" (1%) reference is made to DARIAH's financial contribution to the organisation of the DH2023 in Graz, the Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon or the DARIAH days in Romania.

d) Focus on personnel costs

Although personnel costs are the largest item of expenditure, this does not reflect an excessive administration but rather a strong and diverse team that works directly to support the research communities and meet their needs in terms of communication, research policy, service development, etc. It should be noted that the above-mentioned personnel costs do not take into account the work carried out in the framework of the European projects. Below is the composition of the DARIAH central team:

Staff Costs – administration	FTE
Directors	1,5
Secretary-General	0,9
Legal and administration officer	0,8
European project manager	0,9

Staff Costs – support for the community	FTE
Outreach and communications officer	1
Chief technology officer	0,5
EU project officer (SSHOC project) / Officer for service development	1
Open Science officer	0,7
Working group coordinators and experts for in-kind contributions	0,8
Officer for national coordination	0,6
Training and education officer	0,8

- On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS), Project number 101079608
- PALOMERA – Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA), Project number 101094270
- The Second implementation project for the ERIC Forum (ERIC Forum 2), Grant agreement number, Project number 101124559

In 2023, the operational costs related to European projects are distributed as follows:

Breakdown by projects	Credit	Debit
TRIPLE	33,052 €	33,052 €
EOSC Future	70,607 €	70,607 €
CLS Infra	28,188 €	28,188 €
OPERAS-Plus	7,053 €	7,053 €
PALOMERA	15,732 €	15,732 €
ERIC Forum 2	3,176 €	3,176 €
Total European projects	157,809 €	157,809 €

Breakdown by type of costs	2023
Personnel costs	146,654 €
Travel and accommodation	10,039 €
Catering	1,116 €
Total	157,809 €

2) European projects

a) Financial overview

DARIAH's participation in several European projects requires a specific financial monitoring according to the rules set up by the European Commission. Consequently, the resources and expenses related to EU projects are accounted for separately for transparency purposes.

In 2023, DARIAH was involved in the following projects:

- Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration (TRIPLE), Grant agreement number 863420
- EOSC future (EOSC Future), Project number 101017536
- Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA), Project number 101004984

DARIAH-EU

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

DARIAH ERIC
Head Office
IR* Huma-Num, CNRS UAR 3598
54 Boulevard Raspail
75006 Paris
France

DARIAH ERIC
Coordination Office Berlin
Centre Marc Bloch
Friedrichstraße 191
10117 Berlin
Germany

www.dariah.eu
info@dariah.eu